

Parallels between crude oil prices, the spillover of American monetary policy, and Indo-American trade and their impact on Indian inflation.

Introduction

Inflation, which refers to an increase in an economy's price level over time, is also stimulated due to innumerable external factors in globalized and liberated emerging economies such as BRICS nations. Examining Indian inflation is the main focus of this research. This area is worth studying because it thoroughly examines the cons developing liberated markets face in their economic activity due to external factors. This, allows policymakers to ponder additional solutions for tackling inflation when contractionary demand side policies do not aid the circumstances, leading to scope for creativity in solutions to tackle issues concerning the economic well-being of 1.4 billion humans.

As India's energy requirements have steadily increased, from consuming 3474.661 barrels/per day to 5147.576 barrels per day,¹ so have its import of crude oil, making it the third largest consumer of oil after the United States and China, respectively.² In contrast, this developing nation imports 85% of its oil requirements and is a major trading partner of OPEC countries, the top five countries from which India imports its crude oil are: Iran, the USA, Nigeria, Saudi Arabia, and UAE. In the energy dynamics of this economy, oil is undoubtedly a major factor because it makes up 30% of India's primary energy consumption, with coal, mineral oil, thermal power, hydro and other fossil fuels accounting for the remaining 70%. Nonetheless, as of now, the dependence on imports is an essential factor that makes Indian Inflation, more specifically India's WPI- fuel and power (wholesale price index), vulnerable to fluctuating oil prices. A negative oil shock is generally of greater concern to firms since it translates directly into increased production costs. Besides, industries directly exposed to petroleum affect other industries equally because higher oil prices increase the prices of other commodities related to the input. In addition, researchers found that a \$5 per barrel sustained rise in oil prices in India would result in an inflation rise by 1.3 percentage points with a year lag (Bhattacharya & Bhattacharyya, 2001). Oil prices are, therefore, a significant factor in determining inflation and the rationale for government-enforced fuel subsidy policies.

¹ [India Oil Consumption, 1965 – 2022 | CEIC Data](#)

²Market, Capital. 2016. “Ind-Ra: India to Remain the Third Largest Consumer of Crude in the Next Decade”, Business Standard. June 29
https://www.business-standard.com/article/news-cm/ind-ra-india-to-remain-the-third-largest-consumer-of-crude-in-the-next-decade-116062900213_1.html#:~:text=As%20per%20the%20latest%20BP,mbpd

The dollar appreciation weakens INR, making any trade in dollars more expensive for an emerging economy like India. Weak domestic currency makes imports expensive, commodities specifically, increasing domestic inflation. However, the negative spillover of American monetary policy is also a contributor to Indian inflation, which will be explored in this research. Several papers have touched upon Inflation in India stimulated by crude oil prices and the negative spillover impact of American monetary policy on Inflation targeting nations, but they have not been specific to the unique Indian economic background; moreover, they focus on high financial dollarization while considering diplomatic implications. This paper tries to answer: **How** crude oil prices, spillover of American monetary policy, and Indo-American trade contributed to Indian Inflation between the period 2011 to 2022, by plotting and combining trend graphs along with economic analysis.

Literature review

Previous research explores seven inflation-targeting developing economies and the influence of the spillovers from monetary policy uncertainty in the United States on these countries' policy rates, which included Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Indonesia, Mexico, Poland, and South Africa (Azad & Serletis, 2022). It is useful as it helps this research understand the impact of US monetary policy on emerging markets. To reach their conclusions, the authors employ monthly data, starting the sample duration at the introduction of the inflation targeting in the respective economies; moreover, the research employs a Garch in mean vector autoregression, a statistical model, used to record a relationship between multiple variables as they change over time. The conclusion drawn by the authors from the evidence of this particular research is that regardless of how the US monetary policy uncertainty is measured; it has negative implications on the financial and macroeconomic framework.

Moreover, (Bhattacharya & Bhattacharyya, 2001) previous studies also underscore the cruciality of crude oil as a price determinant along with several other commodities because an increase or a decrease in its price has a direct impact on the prices of various commodities and society. This particular research also helped formulate a part of the methodology employed in this paper, as the researchers point out that a \$5 sustained rise in oil prices in India would result in an inflation rise by 1.3 percentage points with a year lag. The eminent factor of a year lag led to the usage of India's WPI fuel and power instead of the annual Inflation rate as a marker of increase in price levels; this was also done to avoid the inconvenience of presenting a year lag on a graph while superimposing multiple trends.

Not to mention, Eichenbaum and Evans (1995) found a strong connection between monetary policy and the exchange rate, a connection not supported by prevailing literature of that time. Contractionary monetary policy in the US results in a sustained appreciation in US nominal and real exchange rates.³This appreciation of the dollar weakens currencies like the INR, thus,

³ Real exchange rates: Adjusted to inflation

increasing the costs associated with imports, including commodities, which will later increase the price levels of the economies with depreciating currencies.⁴

Raj, Dhal, Jain (2008) proved that exchange rate, import prices, and capital flows had a long-term, statistically meaningful positive correlation with domestic inflation. The interest rate variable negatively affected domestic prices in the long run. However, its statistical significance was not as strong as other variables. According to this study, the impact of domestic prices and capital flows was more prominent than the impact of import prices and exchange rates. The conclusions of this study implied that transnational factors such as capital flows, movements in the exchange rate, and import prices contribute to 20 to 30 percent of domestic inflation in India.

Methodology

While previous literature provides insight into the macroeconomic implications of American monetary policy spillover on developing nations, though it is not specific to India, it also highlights the nature of Indian inflation and the impact of crude oil prices on it. However, they are not based on recent trends. In order to further the findings, the paper will include the trend of Indian inflation from 2011 to 2022, a period of 10 years. However, for superimposing trend lines, this research used India's WPI fuel and power figures instead of the annual inflation rate to avoid any inaccuracies due to a time lag, as mentioned previously. The expected results are that India's increasing reliance on OPEC oil imports makes India's WPI vulnerable to oil shocks and volatility in its exchange rate with the US. Furthermore, this research will be integrating the trend of the US federal funds rate and its impacts on Indian inflation to further assert that an increase in the federal funds rate would appreciate USD. This will devalue the INR and as the currency used for India's oil transactions is dollars, the cost of the imported crude oil increases because the dollar is stronger. Thus, giving rise to the WPI. Lastly, to validate the claims, the research will overlay the movement of oil prices from the Indian basket onto the WPI fuel and power.

Data Analysis

Inflation through Oil

⁴ INR: Indian rupee

Figure 1: Annual Indian Inflation 2011-June 2022

Source: IMF

Understanding Indian Inflation and the key economic events affecting the shape of this representation is paramount to understanding this research; Figure 1 portrays the trend of the Indian inflation rate from 2011 to July 2022. The Indian inflation rate saw one of the lowest changes in percentage from 2016 to 2017 due to the demonetization of all 500 and 1000 rupee notes, wiping out 86% of the country's currency overnight.⁵The aftermath of the decision accounted for decreased liquidity and cash flow in the Indian market, which drove down the rate of Inflation (Anjali Ahuja, Sakshi Anand 2001). After steady growth in Inflation from 2018 to 2020, the price level witnessed a steep decrease due to the COVID-19 pandemic as consumer spending fell drastically. Since September 2021, spikes in crude oil prices and increases in commodity prices caused by the Russia-Ukraine war have resulted in a sharp rise in Inflation in India.

⁵ Vanamali, Krishna. 2021. "Demonetisation, 5 years on: Key economic indicators paint a mixed picture", Business Standard, November 8
https://www.business-standard.com/podcast/economy-policy/demonetisation-5-years-on-key-economic-indicators-paint-a-mixed-picture-121110700971_1.html#:~:text=On%20November%20%2C%202016%2C%20Prime,86%25%20of%20India's%20currency%20overnight

Figure 2: OPEC's share of India's oil imports

Source: Reuters

Figure 2 mainly displays the share of OPEC nations in India's oil imports as a percentage. Increasing reliance on imports is believed to exacerbate a country's vulnerability to the effects of oil shocks as risks occur in the oil-importing process (C. Lacasse, A. Plourde 1995). As it can be seen, the Indian oil imports largely depend on OPEC nations, leading to the question of to what extent changes in oil prices affect the Indian WPI fuel and power. In the current environment, region-specific trends suggest that industrial and oil exporting countries played an essential role in global trade inflation

Figure 3: Crude oil prices (Indian basket) vs. Indian WPI fuel and power

Crude oil prices (Indian basket) vs Indian WPI fuel and power

Source: eaindustry. nic.in (office of economic advisor), petroleum planning and analysis cell (PPAC)

Figure 3 charts the relationship between the crude oil prices in the Indian basket with the country's fuel and power WPI from 2011 to July 2022. The correlation coefficient of these two variables is 0.33 from 2011 to 2015 and 0.68 from 2016 to 2022, the last hints toward a strong correlation. A point of exception was the period between 2012 to 2013 when the Indian WPI fuel and power witnessed a drastic decrease which was essentially due to temporary issues like stronger currency and weaker domestic demand, coupled with structural factors like better food management taking Indian inflation which was more than a record high 11% (seen in figure 1) in 2012 to a mere 2.2% in 2017, lower than the UK, Mexico, and Turkey at that time.⁶ Indian CPI or inflation would not follow the same trend or strongly correlate with increasing oil prices because of the time lag mentioned above. Moreover, crude oil prices affect Indian inflation indirectly. Thus, it is of esteem importance to compare the closest index on which a sudden impact of change in oil prices can be observed; in this case, it is the WPI fuel and power.

⁶ Nag, Anirban and Goyal, Karthik. 2017. "From 11% to 2.2%, five charts that explain India's vanishing inflation". Economic Times, June 20

<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/economy/indicators/from-11-to-2-2-five-charts-explain-vanishing-india-inflation/articleshow/59227745.cms>

Inflation Through American Monetary Policy and Trade

The paper will discover how the American monetary policy contributes to changes in India's macroeconomic sphere, specifically inflation. The rate-setting Federal Open Market Committee on May 25, 2022, stated that "Most participants judged that 50 basis point increases in the target range would likely be appropriate at the next couple of meetings." The FOMC may adopt a more restrictive policy stance based on the evolving economic outlook and associated risks. The rupee has been negatively impacted by tight monetary policy worldwide. The rupee was at an all-time low against the US dollar at an average of 79.56 for August 2022, which can be attributed to the outflow of foreign investments due to geopolitical uncertainties on the Russia-Ukraine war, as well as tighter US monetary policy. When a central bank decreases its interest rates, it will mostly lead to a depreciation of that country's currency and an appreciation in the exchange rates if the policy rate is raised. A depreciation would make imports more expensive while improving the price competitiveness of that country's exports. Making the channel of exchange rate of monetary policy crucial for several developing economies, as its impact on their economy is evident.

Exchange rate pass-through translates exchange rate changes into the price of imports in the importing market's currency. The requirement for the exchange rate pass-through to function optimally relies on the assumption that exporters will alter the home prices of their goods or service so that the price in the importing country is unchanged. Exporters have a choice to either absorb the impact of the change in the exchange rate on the importing nation or make necessary changes to their margins so that it does not affect the market shares in the importing nation. Market power in the importing nation determines the extent to which exchange rate changes are passed through, which is itself determined by the degree of competition in the market. ERPT can be divided into two stages: one involves changes in import prices caused by exchange rate fluctuations; the second involves the burden or benefit of changes in import prices being passed on to consumers and wholesale prices of the importing country (Venkataramana Yanamandra, 2015). VAR model of exchange rate and inflation would showcase that the impact of Exchange rate pass-through is considerably higher for emerging markets than for developed economies (Calvo and Reinhart 2000).

Figure 4: American federal funds rate

Source: Macrotrends

Globally economies are in a recession due to high inflationary pressure. To combat this, the Fed, which is the central bank of the US, has instituted aggressive measures, including raising interest rates to reduce the flow of money in the economy. As higher interest increases the cost of credit in the economy, people and firms take fewer loans, reducing the overall money supply of an economy. Additionally, a higher interest rate makes saving money in the bank more appealing due to higher returns. Both of these factors, thus, aid in reducing the price of goods and services, further reducing Inflation.

Figure 4 graphs the American federal funds rate trend from 2011 to 2022. The rise in the Fed funds rate is represented by the steep increase from 2021 to 2022. During this period of monetary tightening by the US Fed, portfolio investment outflows were triggered in India. Till May 16, 2022, foreign portfolio investors had withdrawn USD 21.2 billion from India. Besides a higher import bill, the investment outflow has put sudden pressure on the Indian rupee and forex reserve. The fall in the Indian rupee, majorly due to the outflow of foreign investments, made imported items costlier and contributed to Inflation, already being out of the RBI's⁷, favorable range of 2-6 percent. In addition, metals, banking, and fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) are

⁷ Reserve bank of India, India;s central bank

among the affected sectors. Thus, Indian retail Inflation stood at 7.79 percent in April⁸ 2022 (an 8-year high).

Figure 5: India-USA trade

Source: census.gov

One of the major reasons why the Indian economy is vulnerable to American monetary policies or macroeconomic steps is the increase in trade between the two nations. According to recent data from India's Ministry of Trade and Industry, bilateral trade with the US hit \$119.42 billion, leading to the US surpassing China to become India's biggest trading partner. The data show that

⁸Haris, Mohammad. 2022. "US Fed Rate Hikes: Know How It's Impacting Stocks, Rupee, Inflation In India". News 18, May 26
<https://www.news18.com/news/business/us-fed-rate-hikes-know-how-its-impacting-stocks-rupee-inflation-in-india-5252041.html>

imports jumped from approximately USD 29 billion to USD 43.31 billion; India's trade exports to the US increased from USD 51.62 billion in the previous financial year to roughly USD 76.11 billion⁹. Figure 5 portrays the movement of Indian-American trade from 2011 to 2021. India's exports to the US and imports from the US have a positive gradient, except for 2020 when international trade experienced a substantial decline due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The upward trend of Indo-American trade has its cons, precisely, imported inflation. For instance, from the 1950s to the 1990s, India's import price inflation in the USD remained moderate. The measure of import price inflation averaged 5.2 percent, contrary to the slowing movement in the 1980s and 1990s. Lastly, there was a strong link between domestic inflation and import price increases (Raj, Dhal, Jain 2008)

Conclusion

Figure 6: Russian oil imports by China and India

Source: Kpler

⁹ Prerna. 2022. "The US has become India's largest trade partner. Is India-China trade decoupling?". Inventiva, June 24

<https://www.inventiva.co.in/trends/the-us-indias-largest-trade-partner>

After the rupee declined to all-time lows and foreign investors withdrew USD 29 billion, India unveiled a rupee settlement plan to smoothen Russian trade, where the RBI plans to increase imports from Russia and settle international trade in INR. The conclusion of this research will lean towards increasing trade with Russia, as it is appearing as a possible opportunity for India to diversify its energy supplies; furthermore, escalate rupee trade to decrease dependency on the USD to decrease the Indian economy's vulnerability towards oil shocks in the Middle East and volatility in the interest rate. Under the plan proposed by the RBI, the payments made by importers for buying goods and services from outside the country will be in INR, credited to a special account of the correspondent bank of the associate country. At the same time, exporters will be paid from the balances in the designated special account.¹⁰ According to commodities data and analytics firm Kpler, India's crude import from Russia in March 2022 is approximately four times higher than that of import of crude oil from Russia around the same time last year. Furthermore, India's import of Russian oil saw a steep increase since the start of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict, as shown in figure 6. So far, this decision appears to be a strategic move by the Indian government to shield the economy from the adverse effect of the recent surge in global crude oil prices while also exploring the opportunity of importing additional oil from Russia at lower or discounted rates¹¹. And as previously mentioned, the burden or cost caused by a change in import prices is transferred to the consumer and the nation's wholesale prices, affecting India's WPI fuel and power in the short run and CPI in the long run, which would eventually lower the inflation rate, considering a substantial decrease in dependence on Middle Eastern oil and the USD.

Even though this decision will cause India numerous economic benefits like mitigating the risks arising out of geopolitical disruptions and an expectation of price stability, as mentioned by the Indian Ministry Of Petroleum And Natural Gas,¹² the cons lie on the diplomatic front; an increase in Indian-Russian trade will be and have led to a conflict of interest with the USA. The US said that India buying oil from Russia at discounted rates would not violate its sanctions; however, it could potentially “put India on the wrong side of history”¹³, indicating an explicit conflict of interest.

¹⁰ Goyal, Kartik and Mazumdar, Ronojoy. 2022. “India Unveils Rupee Settlement Plan to Smoothen Russia Trade”. Bloomberg, July 11 <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2022-07-11/india-unveils-rupee-settlement-plan-to-smoothen-russia-trade>

¹¹ ANI. 2022. “India-Russia oil trade: What is at stake?”. India Times. March 20 [Crude Oil Prices: India-Russia oil trade: What is at stake?, Auto News, ET Auto \(indiatimes.com\)](#)

¹² Online, FE. 2022. “India will now import oil from Russia; aims for price stability”. Financial Express, February 6 [India will now import oil from Russia; aims for price stability | The Financial Express](#)

¹³ 2022. “Not violation of sanctions but Russian oil deal could put India on wrong side of history, says US”. India Today, March 16 [Not violation of sanctions but Russian oil deal could put India on wrong side of history, says US - World News \(indiatoday.in\)](#)

In the short run, it may ease inflationary pressure caused by an increase in crude oil prices but may tarnish India's relations with the West, turning out to be a battle between economic and diplomatic interests.

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Data sets

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